

Learning symbolic expressions to solve multi-period time slot pricing vehicle routing problems

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Abstract

In the realm of omnichannel retail and logistics optimization, this paper introduces the Multi-period Time Slot Pricing Vehicle Routing Problem and addresses it using a Genetic Programming approach within a Markov Decision Process framework. The proposed method aims to maximize the profit of an omnichannel retailer by learning symbolic expressions that guide sequential decision-making transparently and efficiently. Customer time slot preferences and system dynamics are simulated, enabling the evaluation of various pricing strategies and routing decisions. At the conclusion of each booking horizon, a Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows is solved to serve booked customers and reveal transportation costs. Through experimental evaluation, we demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in achieving higher profits compared to a baseline panel used by the European retailer that inspired this work, while maintaining interpretability, crucial for real-world deployment. We analyze the behavior of symbolic decision policies under four different customer choice model configurations. Our findings underline the significance of explainable Artificial Intelligence techniques in optimizing complex logistics systems, paving the way for enhanced integrated pricing and transportation decisions in Attended Home Delivery.

1 Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of omnichannel retail, where customer expectations for seamless, efficient delivery experiences continue to soar, the optimization of logistics operations has become paramount. With the grocery delivery market worldwide set to achieve a staggering revenue of US\$782.40bn by the year 2024 [Statista, 2023], the pressure on retailers to streamline their delivery processes while maximizing profits has never been greater.

One of the challenges that is faced by omnichannel retailers is a pricing problem where delivery time slot fees are decided, a complex dynamic optimization problem that requires balancing customer preferences with operational efficiency and

profitability. After selecting a set of products, (i.e., a shopping basket), customers are shown a time slot panel so that they can choose a time slot to receive their purchase in an Attended Home Delivery (AHD). The omnichannel retailer can dynamically decide the delivery fee of each time slot, trying to maximize its profit. If the price of the time slots is too high, customers may walkaway. If the price of the most desirable time slots is too low, logistics capacity (i.e. number of trucks), may not be sufficient to serve all customers. Dynamic pricing is a technique used to find strategies for changing the price over time of a selling product based on changing circumstances [Ferrara, 2018]. In many cases, compared to a static price policy, dynamic pricing is a win-win situation, both for the company and the customer [Chen and Gallego, 2019]. Traditional approaches to this problem have often fallen short, struggling to adapt to the dynamic nature of modern retail environments and failing to provide transparent decision-making mechanisms that resonate with operations managers. For instance, in [Strauss *et al.*, 2021], a linear programming approach is adeptly utilized to tackle a dynamic pricing challenge within the realm of AHD. Here, customers are presented with a choice between standard and flexible delivery windows. Opting for the latter not only offers a reduced price but also affords the company greater flexibility in route planning. The literature has been considering disregarding important real-world features, such as multiple periods, multiple vehicles, and realistic customer time slot choice models.

This paper introduces the Multi-period Time Slot Pricing Vehicle Routing Problem (MPTSPVRP) and presents a novel solution approach leveraging the power of Genetic Programming (GP) [Koza, 1993] within a Markov Decision Process (MDP) framework [Puterman, 1994]. The choice of GP is motivated by the need for explainable symbolic expressions that can provide insights into the decision-making process, empowering operations managers to understand and trust the recommendations generated by the Artificial Intelligence (AI) system. By learning symbolic expressions that guide sequential decision-making, our approach aims to unlock new levels of transparency and efficiency in omnichannel logistics optimization.

The main contributions of this work are threefold. First, we model the MPTSPVRP as an MDP to be available to all the research community, as the literature as been focusing on single-period problems ([Agatz *et al.*, 2011], [Klein *et al.*,

2018], [Klein *et al.*, 2019], [Koch and Klein, 2020], [Akerman *et al.*, 2022]. Second, we devise a GP approach to devise symbolic decision policies that are explainable-by-design. Third, we present preliminary results on the efficiency and transparency achieved by the learned decision policies when facing different types of customer preferences (i.e., customer choice models).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we detail the MPTSPVRP and present the MDP devised to model it. Section 3 presents the GP framework that was used to learn symbolic expressions to be used as decision policies. In Section 4, we present the computational experiments and insights obtained from some operation managers in the company. Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions and future research directions that emerged from this work.

2 Problem definition

The problem setting we address in this work is a MPTSPVRP, commonly encountered in online or e-commerce platforms offering AHD. In these platforms, customers select products, place them in a shopping basket, and then proceed to check-out. At this point, they are prompted to select a preferred time slot from a panel with the available time slots and respective delivery fee. Delivery fees may vary based on delivery time, day of the week, accepted and expected demand, and other business considerations. After the cutoff time, when no more orders are accepted, the operations manager plans the delivery routes with the available fleet.

The MPTSPVRP involves dynamically optimizing price panels to allocate limited logistics resources efficiently to customers. For each incoming customer, the online retailer chooses the best time slots to be shown and their corresponding prices. The objective is to maximize total profit, where the total revenue is composed of the basket values and delivery fees collected, and the total cost is associated with transportation cost comprising fleet and traveling cost. This problem poses a sequential decision-making problem under uncertainty and can be formalized as a MDP. A schematic overview of a decision epoch of this problem is presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: An example of a customer arriving with a price panel to be shown. Some customers are already booked and can be seen on the map. One customer so far walked away.

2.1 The MPTSPVRP as a MDP

We modeled the problem as a MDP. We can define the MDP tuple (S, A, P, R) , where S is the state space (including

problem-related features), A is the action space (the possible price panels to be shown), P is the transition probability function (considering realistic customer choice models), and R is the reward function (characterizing revenue and transportation cost). The system begins at an initial state s_0 and a new decision epoch k is triggered whenever a new customer arrives at the online platform, leaving the system at state s_k . This continues until the final state s_K is reached, when the final customer of the considered booking horizon arrives.

States. State s_0 contains the static information about the environment, summarized in Table 1. States s_k contain the necessary information to describe the system sufficiently. For this problem, when a new customer arrives at a new decision epoch k , the available information includes information about the logistics system (e.g., how many customers have been accepted in each time slot) and about the new customer (e.g., location, basket value, historical time windows choices, etc).

Actions. The possible actions $\mathbf{a}_k \in A_k(s_k)$ at each decision epoch k correspond to the possible presentable price panels. A price panel is a vector of delivery fees, $\mathbf{a}_k = (f_{wdk})_{wd \times 1}$, such that f_{wdk} represents the delivery fee charged for time slot at time w and day d . The decision of the price panel impacts whether a customer walks away (no-purchase option) or accepts a certain time slot. The notation $(f_{wdk})_{wd \times 1}$ indicates that the action vector \mathbf{a}_k is composed of elements f_{wdk} , arranged in a vector of size $wd \times 1$.

Transitions. A system transition occurs when the customer, faced with the price panel \mathbf{a}_k , chooses a time slot or alternatively, drops out on the purchase. For the former, the system transitions from state s_k to a new state, $s_{k+1} = \Gamma(s_k, wd)$, with probability $\mathbb{P}_{wd}(\mathbf{a}_k)$. The probability of the customer dropping out is $\mathbb{P}_0(\mathbf{a}_k) = 1 - \sum_{w \in \Delta} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \mathbb{P}_{wd}(\mathbf{a}_k)$. The transition probabilities (i.e., choice probabilities) are not fully known by the retailer but can be inferred with historical customer choice data and business understanding, resulting in the modeling of a customer choice model. In [Amorim *et al.*, 2024], the impact of customers' loyalty to the retailer, basket value, basket size, and basket composition on their willingness to pay is quantified. Also, the offered time slot characteristics, such as speed, precision and timing, can influence the customer preferences. Understanding this interactions is crucial to realistically model the reaction of customers to the provided time slot options and respective prices.

Rewards. Given the objective to maximize profit, an immediate reward of a decision epoch k is composed of the basket value b_k , the delivery fee f_{wdk} , and a transportation cost c_k . Note that the transportation cost component is only positive for $k = K$, at the end of an episode, when the vehicle routes are defined by solving a Vehicle Routing Problem With Time Windows (VRPTW) considering the scheduled customers. In the final state, the reward is expected to be negative, as it will absorb all transportation costs. In each decision epoch, the immediate reward r_k is given by

$$r_k = b_k + f_{wdk} - c_k \quad (1)$$

Objective function. The objective function is to maximize the sum of the accumulated revenue throughout the booking horizon minus the transportation cost imputed at the end of each episode by solving a VRPTW. Let π be a sequence of

actions $\mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_K$ for every decision epoch $k = 0, \dots, K$. The aim is to find an optimal policy π that maximizes the total expected profit. The objective function, conditional on initial state s_0 , is the following

$$\max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^K r_k | s_0 \right] \quad (2)$$

Solving the aforementioned MDP involves finding an optimal policy π^* that maps each action $\mathbf{a}_k \in A_k(s_k)$ to choose in $s_k \in S$. This means that, at each system state, the policy will indicate the price panel that maximizes the expected cumulative reward over time, aligning with the goal of maximizing profit. Let us denote $V_{\pi}(s_k)$ as the value function that gives the total expected reward if we start from a state s_k and follow policy π . This value includes the immediate reward received at decision epoch $k + 1$ and the expected rewards to obtain in the future until the final decision epoch K . Our objective is to find a sequence of actions that maximizes the total reward obtained through the entire process. Considering the Bellman Equation [Powell, 2007], $V^*(s_k) = \max_{\mathbf{a}_k \in A(s_k)} \{r_{k+1} + \mathbb{E}[V(s_{k+1}) | s_k, a]\}$, an optimal action \mathbf{a}_k^* , meaning the price panel providing the best expected value, is implemented by solving the following expression,

$$\mathbf{a}_k^* = \arg \max_{\mathbf{a}_k \in A(s_k)} \{r_{k+1} + \mathbb{E}[V(s_{k+1}) | s_k, a]\} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Explainability in MDPs

The explainability properties of MDPs are not extensively studied in the literature. However, in this context, explaining different parts of the decision policy can be valuable both for operations managers and, finally, for the online retail customers. We have explored several possibilities to disclose the explainability properties of the decision policies that are learned using the MDP presented in Section 2.1.

We emphasize the sequential nature of the MPTSPVRP, where new information is revealed over multiple periods, and decisions have both direct and delayed effects on outcomes. Thus, one approach involves exploring the explainability properties for the entire sequence of actions on the entire system [Stratis Tsirtsis, 2021]. It entails understanding why the system followed a particular trajectory and how the sequence of actions or policy contributed to the final objective of maximizing profit. Through counterfactuals, exploring "what-if" scenarios, such as considering how changes in operational parameters (e.g., maximum allowed fee) would affect the overall profitability of the operation, provides valuable insights to the operations manager. However, due to the sequential aspect of the problem, running counterfactual explanations of this nature requires simulating the entire operation, which can be challenging due to the high uncertainty in state transitions and the interdependency of stochastic events.

Alternatively, we can explore explainability properties at the action selection level. In the MPTSPVRP context, a decision corresponds to a price panel recommendation. By extracting insights into the factors considered by the price panel recommendation and providing policy explanations, we can offer valuable insights to both operations managers and customers. This includes explaining how state features influence

panel recommendations (e.g., customers with larger baskets are shown panels with lower prices so that they do not walk-away) and providing counterfactual explanations (e.g., if the customer's basket value was 50% larger, the fees would be 10% lower).

MDPs allow us to learn a policy for selecting actions based on the current state, yet understanding the rationale behind a specific action choice can be an intricate task. Such understanding hinges on how the policy was learned or parameterized. In complex environments, such as the one we aim at solving, interpreting these actions can be particularly challenging, especially when employing intricate parameterization methods like Neural Networks, due to the complexity and opaque nature of such methods. An explainable-by-design approach presents a promising solution to alleviate these challenges. In the context of MPTSPVRPs, we consider deriving a policy represented by a simple symbolic expression as an explainable-by-design approach. By expressing the decision policy in clear mathematical functions and logical rules with a controlled size (i.e., reasonable for human understanding according to the opinion of the humans who will use the expressions), transparency and interpretability are prioritized in the decision-making process.

3 Solution approach

In this work we derive symbolic expressions to serve as decision policies in the MPTSPVRPs. This is of utmost importance for operations managers dealing with this sequential decision problem as (1) they aim at understanding the decision policy being used, (2) they are able to contribute with explainable features that they understand, and (3) they can participate in the improvement process of symbolic expressions (i.e., participate in the learning loop). In section 3.1 we explain the learning process adopted to learn symbolic expressions. Then, in Sections 3.2 and 3.3 we detail our procedure to define the terminals and operators to be used in the learning process.

3.1 Genetic programming for symbolic policy search

To learn symbolic expression for the MPTSPVRP, we use a GP approach [Koza, 1993]. GP can be employed to evolve decision policies that map states to actions, effectively learning decision policies that maximize the cumulative reward over time. In MPTSPVRPs, GP can generate symbolic expressions that determine scoring strategies to choose a price panel (action) based on the current state of the system (features such as customer location, time of day, current number of bookings, etc.). The quality (fitness) of each evolved decision policy can be evaluated by simulating its performance in the MDP environment and computing the cumulative reward obtained over the entire booking horizon. Given that we are using symbolic expressions as decision policies, our decision policies are explainable-by-design. This means that a human is capable of inspecting these decision policies and have a feeling for what their behavior will be.

Our learning framework starts with an initial population of symbolic expressions (individuals), which can be obtained

randomly or read from external sources (e.g., the user knows one or more efficient symbolic expressions he wishes to consider). Then, at each iteration, each symbolic expression will be evaluated while solving the MDP, making several decisions per episode. Figure 2 shows a reduced-scale example of a panel choice in a decision epoch. Due to the stochasticity of the choice model and the randomness of customer location and arrival times, the same expression leads to different fitness results for each evaluation. In order to reduce this variation, the fitness is computed as the average reward within several episodes. After the evaluation of the population, the GP algorithm will select a set of individuals to be preserved (elitism) and sets of individuals to be mutated or crossed over. Through iterations of selection, crossover, and mutation operations, GP can evolve increasingly effective decision policies that adapt to the dynamics of the problem, ultimately leading to improved revenue generation (basket value and fees) and cost management (transportation cost). An overview of this process is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 2: An example of the scoring process of a panel with different expressions. In the example, only price features are used. If the considered features can summarize the information about the already accepted clients, the decision policy given by the expression will consider the system’s dynamism.

3.2 User-guided feature engineering

A significant part of the work involved in developing efficient decision policies using GP entails the selection of the features (called terminals in GP literature) to be used by the symbolic expressions. In this case, the GP algorithm developers discussed important terminals to figure in the symbolic expressions, based on their retail business understanding. Furthermore, in the context of a GP learning loop, it is also possible for a human agent (the operations manager) to detect a missing feature in the terminals provided to the GP algorithm.

Figure 3: Learning framework considering symbolic expressions as decision agents to be used in a MDP. The learning process stops after a certain number of iterations is achieved (typically users do not have an idea of what is a good fitness).

Table 1: Instance parameters used to generate replications.

Parameter name	Description
Region	Porto, Porto, Portugal
Depot location	Randomly generated
Number of vehicles	10
Vehicle capacity (orders)	10
Extra vehicle daily cost (€)	300
Cost per kilometer (€)	0.40
Service time (minutes)	10
Booking horizon (days)	3
Customer arrival rate (customers/day)	30
Baseline price	6.99
Number of pre-defined panels	41
Routing solver	HGS [Kool <i>et al.</i> , 2022]

This missing feature is then added to the terminal set. Typically, at an initial phase, the nodes of a GP tree are based on single features, but they can also be pre-built expressions suggested by domain experts, such as the operations managers in this case.

3.3 User-guided operator selection

Although there are multiple ways to define the operators (e.g., sum, subtraction, division, multiplication, etc.) to be considered in the symbolic expressions, we opted to discuss them with a team of operations managers. These operations managers, despite having a high educational level (bachelor or above), opted for simple operators that they could easily understand in an isolated form.

4 Computational experiments

In this section we describe the considered problem instances (Section 4.1), the adopted GP algorithm parameters (Section 4.2), the considered customer choice model configurations (Section 4.3), and the results obtained in terms of algorithm convergence and business metrics performance (Section 4.4).

4.1 Instances

The instances considered in our experiments are generated in each episode using the parameters described in Table 1. Each episode, also called replication, is generated with some degree of uncertainty (e.g., unknown customer arrival times). With these parameters, we intend to realistically simulate the delivery operations of the considered omnichannel retailer.

The booking horizon is composed of 3 days where customers arrive at a constant rate of 30 customers per day. At the end of the booking horizon no more customers will be accepted, and vehicle routes need to be generated to serve the booked orders. The omnichannel retailer has a fleet of 10 homogeneous vehicles to be used in each day. If the number of used vehicles exceeds this limit, additional vehicles must be rented at an extra cost of 300€. Each vehicle has the capacity to serve 10 orders and the delivery service time at each customer is of 10 minutes.

Our MPTSPVRP simulation environment ¹, implemented as an OpenAI gym [Brockman *et al.*, 2016], has a set of predefined price panel options, which is fixed and of a controlled size due to the retailer constraints. We utilized a set of 41 price panels. The retailer offers a baseline panel with fixed time slot prices where all time slots are priced uniformly at 6.99. The remaining panels offer variations on this baseline panel, adjusting prices for specific groups of slots based on factors such as period of the day, slot timing, and day of the week (e.g., cheap Monday).

4.2 GP parameters

Our GP algorithm is a simple implementation using DEAP [Fortin *et al.*, 2012]. Different symbolic tree depths were tested in order to understand the tree depth impact in the generated expressions performance. Furthermore, to incorporate the inputs of the operations managers, we decided to consider 6 simple operators to figure in the symbolic expression, willing to keep them easier to explain. This rationale was also followed when defining the terminals set, which was developed jointly with operations managers. Table 2 presents the main parameters used.

Each training session performed considers population of 25 individuals and runs for 25 generations. This means that, potentially, 625 different symbolic expressions are tested for each set of parameters. Each run takes approximately 3.5 hours to be completed. We set the mutation rate to 75%, the crossover rate to 25%, and an elitism of 10%. We considered maximum tree depths between 1 and 5, for a total of 20 runs including the 4 customer choice model configurations.

The term "replications" refers to the number of times each individual is evaluated. The fitness of the individual is given by the average of each evaluation, in order to reduce the stochasticity introduced by the customer choice model and the randomness of customer location, basket and arrival time.

The designated terminals provide a means of distinguishing among the different price panels, taking into consideration various factors such as slot prices (average, maximum, and minimum), the logistics system state (both chronologically and in terms of existing bookings), customer data (proximity to the depot and analysis of customer baskets), and the relationship between the customer and previous bookings (distance to nearest and farthest booked customers).

4.3 Customer choice models

To evaluate the applicability of GP in addressing MPTSPVRPs, 4 configurations were defined, all characterized by

¹The gym environment files can be found at <https://github.com/fnssm26/MPTSPVRP>.

Table 2: GP algorithm parameters. The operator and terminal sets include inputs from the operations managers to keep expressions at a human-understandable level.

GP parameter	Description
Generations	25
Population size	25
Elitism rate	10%
Replications	3
Minimum tree depth	1
Maximum tree depth	1 to 5
Mutation rate	0.75
Crossover rate	0.25
Operators set	{+, -, *, /, min, max}
Terminal set	{ Cheapest_Slot_Price Most_Expensive_Slot_Price Avg_Slot_Price Current_Time Day_Time Basket_Value Avg_Booked_Basket Avg_Booked_Fee Distance_To_Depot Distance_To_Nearest_Booked Distance_To_Farthest_Booked Vehicle_Capacity }

the attributes outlined in Table 1. What sets these configurations apart is the considered customer choice model, which dictates how customers respond to the presented panel, determining which time slot they choose or if they opt to walkaway (no-purchase option). These customer choice model configurations are outlined as follows:

Accept all: Customers exhibit a strong indifference towards pricing, willing to pay even high delivery fees, resulting in rare walkaway events and consistently choosing a delivery time slot from those provided. Even when presented with the most expensive slot prices, the customer will conclude the purchase process 80% of the times.

Reject expensive: Customers display limited flexibility regarding price and are prone to walking away if the offered options exceed their willingness to pay by even a small margin.

Time based: Features customers with varying price flexibility based on the time of day, with a higher willingness to pay post-midday.

Realistic: Presents the most intricate model, wherein customer willingness to pay correlates with basket value. Additionally, when presented with similarly valuable options, customers tend to favor the cheapest one.

While the first 3 configurations deviate from real-world dynamics, they serve as tools for gauging the learning capabilities of the GP algorithm and the underlying rationale guiding the generated symbolic expressions. For **Accept all** and **Reject expensive** configurations, the generated expressions are anticipated to heavily rely on cost-related terminals such as Avg_Slot_Price, Cheapest_Slot_Price, and Most_Expensive_Slot_Price. Conversely, for the **Time based** configuration, the expressions are expected to incorporate time attributes. The fourth configuration, with a **Realistic** choice model, is expected to demand the consideration of various features, ranging from basket value to temporal informa-

Figure 4: Average fitness across generations for each tested max tree depth and choice model configuration.

tion, also including distance-based factors, like distance to nearest and farthest customers.

4.4 Numerical results

In this section we present the results regarding GP algorithm convergence observed during the training sessions, and decision policy comparison in terms of business metrics performance.

Training - Fitness convergence

In the training sessions of each of the 4 customer choice model configurations, we tested different symbolic tree depths to explore the impact of the size of symbolic expressions in the fitness, i.e. profit, obtained. It is expected that the fitness of larger expressions takes longer to converge and can achieve higher performance. On the other hand, larger expressions will be, probably, less explainable and interpretable to most operations managers. This expected behavior is not observable in Figure 4, as we could not find a significant difference between the tested tree depths. This behavior may be related to the simplicity of the choice models adopted in the tests. We observe that the average fitness of the population converges in few generations, which indicates that either the symbolic expressions can easily capture the complexity of the problem, or we should develop better features to capture additional profit that is not being captured. We also present a dashed line with the maximum fitness obtained (average considering 3 replications) in the final population, the best symbolic expression. The best performance is obtained for the **Accept all** configuration, in which we take advantage of the customer’s high willingness to pay and present more expensive panels. Conversely, the lowest average fitness is obtained for the **Realistic** configuration, where, probably, our approach could not capture all the complex nuances of customer behavior.

Testing - Policy comparison

In Table 3, the performance of 3 types of decision policy is compared across the 4 considered configurations. We compare GP-based policies against a random policy, which chooses price panels randomly, and the baseline panel adopted by the omnichannel retailer that inspired this work, with a static price across all time slots.

The tested expressions were chosen considering a trade-off between explainability and performance, according to discussions with the operations managers. All of them have a reduced depth, making them easy to grasp. The 4 tested expressions correspond to the best individual of the last generation for a certain maximum depth limit. Each policy was tested for 25 episodes, and the presented results correspond to the average between them.

The reasonable performance of the random policy across 4 configurations is related to the fact that the majority of the created panels are in a similar price range, making the customer to evaluate them similarly. This way, choosing one panel over the other (except for the extreme panel settings - much more expensive and much cheaper) has a reduced impact.

The GP expression obtained for the **Accept all** configuration multiplies `Basket_Value` by `Most_Expensive_Slot_Price`. As the `Basket_Value` is the same for all panels, the panels with the higher maximum price are benefited. This way, panels with more expensive time slots are shown, taking advantage of the high willingness to pay of the customer. As panels with more expensive time slots are presented, there is a higher number of walkaways, compared to the other policies. However, the much higher value of the booking fee compensates for the lower number of booked clients. The number of vehicles used per day is also lower, as less deliveries are booked.

The expression tested for the **Reject expensive** configuration only includes terminals that are constant across all panel options. This way, all panels have the same score, and the panel choice becomes random. This justifies the bad performance for this configuration. Ideally, the algorithm would have learned to present the most profitable panels without crossing the customer limit regarding willingness to pay.

In the **Time based** configuration, the expression should be able to distinguish between the 2 customers willing to pay according to the `Day_Time`. This goal was not reached. However, the algorithm learned to present most expensive panels for the entire day, taking advantage of the higher willingness to pay of post midday clients (mean delivery fee is higher). For this reason, both random and baseline policies were out-ranked.

Finally, for the **Realistic** configuration, the results obtained across policies were similar. The generated expression has

Table 3: Policy comparison for the 4 different customer choice model configurations.

Decision policy	Mean Reward	Std Reward	Mean orders	Mean walkaways	Mean basket	Mean fee	Mean transp. cost	Mean vehicles
Accept all								
Baseline	1589.32	165.05	92.72	3.72	12.60	6.99	1.74	4.09
Random	1466.45	134.88	87.88	3.72	12.49	6.78	1.83	3.81
GP: $BASKET_VALUE * MOST_EXPENSIVE_SLOT_PRICE$	2534.47	316.87	89.68	21.68	12.38	26.74	1.91	3.52
Reject expensive								
Baseline	1573.59	183.65	93.28	4.08	12.38	6.99	1.71	3.99
Random	1370.27	193.6	86.48	5.88	12.54	6.26	1.83	3.87
GP: $\min(\frac{VEHICLE_CAPACITY}{AVG_COLLECTED_BASKET}, CURRENT_TIME)$	1518.78	150.79	89.88	3.00	12.55	6.67	1.74	3.89
Time based								
Baseline	675.96	89.42	90.24	50.80	12.59	6.99	2.43	2.60
Random	1225.58	160.36	91.44	19.56	12.44	6.51	1.92	3.48
GP: $\frac{CHEAPEST_SLOT_PRICE}{DISTANCE_TO_FARTHEST_BOOKED + AVG_COLLECTED_BASKET}$	1679.55	285.59	93.60	47.84	12.56	26.52	2.39	2.97
Realistic								
Baseline	973.06	134.36	90.48	34.5	12.54	6.99	2.13	3.19
Random	1023.36	150.61	92.48	32.44	12.92	6.22	2.12	3.33
GP: $\frac{DISTANCE_TO_FARTHEST_BOOKED}{AVG_SLOT_PRICE} - CHEAPEST_SLOT_PRICE + BASKET_VALUE$	1017.10	174.13	87.48	28.12	12.68	6.37	1.94	3.07

the Avg_Slot_Price and Cheapest_Slot_Price attributes as the denominator of a division and as a subtracted element, respectively. This way, most expensive panels are prejudiced. For that reason, most affordable panels were presented, resulting in a lower mean delivery fee.

The GP algorithm has 2 hard-to-achieve objectives. The first one is to understand the customer willingness to pay. If the customer has a higher willingness to pay, we should take advantage of that. This task was well completed for the configuration **Accept all**, as most expensive panels were presented.

The second objective is to increase the profit level with a panel choice accounting for the current state nuances. The relation between the new customer location and the already booked customers coordinates, and also the possibility of offering more attractive panels to the customers with most valuable basket are possible nuances that the algorithm should grasp. This objective was not achieved, probably due to the simple set of terminals and operators adopted.

The most interesting aspect of this approach is the ease of explainability of the designed policy, making this critical analysis possible.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced a novel approach utilizing GP within a MDP framework to tackle the MPTSPVRP in the realm of omnichannel retail and logistics. Our method prioritizes transparency and explainability by generating explainable-by-design symbolic decision policies. These symbolic decision policies can be interpreted by operations managers who are involved in the generation process. Through computational experiments and analysis, we demonstrated the effectiveness of our approach in maximizing profits while maintaining interpretability, outperforming baseline and random panel choice policies in several configurations considering different customer choice models.

Our findings underscore the significance of explainable AI techniques in optimizing complex logistics systems. By incorporating human-guided terminal engineering and operator selection, the generated decision policies are more likely to

remain transparent and understandable, crucial for real-world deployment and operations managers' acceptance. This work not only contributes to the optimization of omnichannel retail operations but also highlights the potential of symbolic learning approaches in addressing intricate decision-making problems.

Future research directions may include the definition of new terminals, through a strong business understanding, to capture the intricate complexities inherent in each state. These terminals could offer heightened precision and depth in evaluating diverse scenarios, thereby enabling more nuanced and accurate solutions to be generated. Moreover, it is important to explore more advanced GP algorithms with powerful optimization capabilities [Virgolin *et al.*, 2021] and interpretability-focused features [Fonseca and Poças, 2023], or even new GP extensions considering constant optimization [Virgolin and Bosman, 2022].

A natural extension of this work is to explore generic decision policies for MPTSPVRPs. In this work, the static parameters (see Table 1) remained consistent across all experiments. Conducting simulations with varied static parameters will result in the development of expressions tailored to different omnichannel retail environments. For instance, the fleet size and the available road network can significantly influence the formulated policy.

Moreover, the future of our GP approach may entangle additional interactions with operations managers, transforming them in important actors in the evolutionary process of symbolic expressions. The analysis presented in Section 4.4 is an example of the benefits of the explainability of the generated expressions. It is easy to follow the rationale behind them as well as to verify their impact across the several metrics results. The idea is to introduce several moments where the operations managers can improve these policies. For instance, introducing hand-crafted symbolic expressions in the initial population, refining some symbolic expressions at the end of a generation, using combined terminals that make sense in their business sector, or even providing feedback in the form of user studies to capture their preferences in terms of performance vs explainability trade-offs.

Ethical Statement

There are no ethical issues.

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